

A new botanical insecticide for managing rice bug

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Rice bug, *Leptocorisa acuta* (Thurnberg), is a serious pest of rice during the crop's reproductive stage. Many synthetic insecticides are used to manage the pest and this resulted in the accumulation of insecticide residues in the harvested produce (Chinniah et al 1998). To identify alternatives to synthetic insecticides, the efficacy of five plant products (see table) against rice bug was tested in irrigated rice (variety ADT36) under field conditions from 1999 to 2002. The experiment used a complete randomized block design with three replications. Fenthion 100 EC 500 mL ha⁻¹ was the check. Plot size was 5 m × 4 m.

Dust formulations of the plant products were prepared by mixing pulverized shade-dried plant with fly ash. Fly ash is a

waste product generated from a thermal power station that uses lignite or coal as fuel. It is an amorphous silicate mineral with major matrix elements such as Si, Ca, K, and Na (Jambagi et al 1995). The dust formulations were then applied using a rotary duster during the milky stage when the bug population reached 8 m⁻². The rice bug population was recorded 3, 7, and 14 d after treatment—i.e., the number of nymphs and adults present in a 1-m² area per plot was observed. The mean population per area and the percentage reduction over the control were determined. Yields were recorded from the entire plot and adjusted to 14% moisture. Among the plant products, *Acorus calamus* 10 D recorded the smallest bug population (3.56 m⁻²), followed by

Nicotiana tabacum 50 D (4.56 m⁻²) and *Ocimum basilicum* 50 D (4.67 m⁻²) (see table). There was a 72.43% reduction in bug population over the check (fly ash control) in *A. calamus* 10 D-treated plots. The same plots recorded a grain yield of 4.5 t ha⁻¹, which was on a par with Fenthion 100 EC 500 mL ha⁻¹ (4.5 t ha⁻¹). The results showed that *A. calamus* 10 D can effectively control the rice bug.

References

- Chinniah C, Kuttalam S, Regupathy A. 1998. Harvest time residue of lindane and chlorpyrifos in paddy. *Pestic. Res. J.* 10 (1):91-94.
- Jambagi AM, Patil CV, Yeldhalli NA, Prakash SS. 1995. Growth and yield of safflower grown on fly ash-amended soil. In: Proceedings of a national seminar on use of lignite fly ash in agriculture. Annamalai Nagar, India. p 79-85.

Effects of selected plant products on rice bug population (mean of three seasons).^a

Treatment	Bug population				Percent decrease over control	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)
	Days after treatment					
	3	7	14	Mean		
<i>Vitex negundo</i> leaf powder at 25 kg ha ⁻¹	8.44 (2.89) d	6.67 (2.56) d	5.54 (2.32) d	6.85 (2.59) d	47.00	3.9 b
<i>Prosopis juliflora</i> leaf powder at 25 kg ha ⁻¹	8.78 (2.96) d	7.11 (2.65) d	5.44 (2.28) cd	7.11 (2.63) d	45.00	3.9 b
<i>Nicotiana tabacum</i> 50 D at 25 kg ha ⁻¹	6.56 (2.54) c	5.33 (2.30) c	4.56 (2.12) c	4.56 (2.12) c	64.70	4.1 b
<i>Acorus calamus</i> 10 D at 25 kg ha ⁻¹	4.00 (1.97) b	3.56 (1.86) b	3.56 (1.84) b	3.56 (1.84) d	72.43	4.5 a
<i>Ocimum basilicum</i> 50 D at 25 kg ha ⁻¹	6.00 (2.43) c	5.00 (2.20) c	4.67 (5.22) c	4.67 (5.22) c	63.85	4.1 b
Fenthion 100 EC at 500 mL ha ⁻¹	1.56 (1.22) a	1.44 (1.16) a	1.41 (1.16) a	1.41 (1.16) a	89.05	4.5 a
Check (fly ash)	13.78 (13.11) e	13.11 (3.60)	12.93 (3.56) e	12.93 (3.56) e		3.8 b

^aNumbers in parentheses are square root-transformed values. Numbers followed by the same letters are not significantly different by LSD ($P=0.05$).